

Dormee

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ABSTRACT

The onset of college life for students poses challenges particularly with the student housing. The current dormitory search process has existing challenges that were identified as traditional search process and fragmented housing information. Dormee steps up as a solution to these problems by offering a platform for students to navigate and secure a housing easily and efficiently. It is a mobile application that helps college students in finding safe, affordable, convenient dormitories near universities. It serves as a centralized digital platform that connects students and landlords while promoting the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities. With the challenges being eliminated, it fosters adequate, safe, affordable housing access for all. The study utilized the Waterfall methodology, approaching a linear and phase-by-phase development and implementation. The application was evaluated using the ISO/IEC 25010 quality standards with a 97% overall rating while the survey testing yielded a “Very Good” interpretation for all assessed criteria. The application shows strong potential for real-world deployment contributing positively to the digital transformation of student housing.

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY CONCEPTS

• Mobile Application Development • UI and UX Design • Database Management Systems • API Integration • Data Analytics • Information Security • Software Development Life Cycle

KEYWORDS

Student Housing, University, Dormitory, Mobile Application, Dormee, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

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1 INTRODUCTION

As students transition into college, they are molded into having a sense of independence, particularly in living independently. Students regarded responsibility and self-management as part of living independently; this includes looking for and securing suitable student housing, a challenging yet crucial task.^[1] Student housing is an accommodation for students that is either on-campus or off-campus.^[2] An important decision for students is choosing the right dormitory as they adapt to independent living.^[3] However, students are facing limited knowledge of available dormitory options, budget constraints, and time and energy demands. Customarily, students have visited dormitories one by one personally, whether they are in the vicinity of their university or not. Since there is a lack of consolidated information about dormitory options, students have inquired about the availability, prices, and amenities, consequently asking the landlords the same set of questions every time, which means there is a need to remember various information in detail across multiple visits. This traditional dormitory search process demanded a great deal of time and energy from students. It is noted that navigating through housing forces students spent considerable time and energy finding suitable housing.^[4] For many students, finding a dormitory that balances affordability, quality, comfort, and convenience is of great importance. Students searched for housing with particular characteristics to satisfy their different needs and preferences.^[2] Hence, they are keen to compare and choose dormitories. As such, searching for dormitories had never been an easy road to take. Hence, there exists a housing crisis among students. A housing crisis is denoted as a state where a significant part of the population is not able to access affordable, safe, and suitable housing.^[4] Researchers found that it has been incredibly challenging for students to access adequate and affordable housing in the early stages of living independently.^[5] Moreover, students emphasized that overcoming the housing crisis required providing better information on housing options; therefore, the problem lies within the fragmented housing information system.^[4]

In line with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (UN SDG) 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities, addressing the challenges, namely, the traditional dormitory search process and the

fragmented housing information system, is at the forefront. This goal emphasized creating more inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable human settlements, which included student housing. By 2030, the goal is to ensure adequate, safe, and affordable housing access for all.^[6] In correlation with this study, United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (UN SDG) 11 is aligned with its purpose and goals: addressing student housing issues, specifically in dormitories, towards better and more accessible housing. The traditional dormitory search process and fragmented system of dormitory information leave students struggling and needing help to secure housing efficiently and effectively. As such, a digitalized and consolidated platform for finding dormitories was implemented, which fostered more accessible and safe housing systems to aid college students as they set foot in college and partake in their independent living. A digitalized platform is the response to the traditional dormitory search process issue, where students no longer need to personally visit dormitories, resolving the inefficiencies in the process. On the other hand, a consolidated platform is a response to the issue of the fragmented housing information system, as underscored in the housing crisis, resolving the problem with access to suitable housing while also offering safety. In all, this equated to the goal of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (UN SDG) 11 and the study itself.

Thus, this study presented Dormee, a mobile application designed to digitalize the dormitory search process and consolidate dormitory information for college students, specifically in Bacolod City. Dormee aimed to simplify the experience of searching for a dormitory by offering a digitalized platform where students view and compare dormitory information digitally through a mobile application. This application provided detailed listings that consolidated dormitory information so that students are able to access essential information. It integrated an expert recommendation module that provided the top three dormitory options tailored to the preferences and needs of the students to help them make better decisions. The application added a scheduling tool where students schedule a visit, either for an in-person viewing, reservation, or settlement, and had it followed up through the chat facility. It is a user-friendly platform with features like geographic information system (GIS) mapping, search, sort, filtering, and bookmarking. Dormee offered transparency and reliability through its features like verified accounts, ratings and reviews, transaction history board, digital contract, notification services, and report module. It also promoted safety and accessibility to housing, which benefited landlords, universities, and related businesses by connecting them with potential tenants. Overall, this study focused on digitalizing the dormitory search process, which involved a consolidated and comprehensive platform for dormitory information and user-centered features.

1.1 Project Scope

The motivation behind Dormee is the drive to address the challenges college students face in finding suitable housing. These challenges include inefficiencies in the traditional dormitory search process and the fragmented housing information system. This application aimed to digitalize the dormitory search process, consolidate dormitory information, and promote the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (UN SDG) 11. The application is intended to eliminate the traditional way of searching for dormitories, saving time and energy. Students weighed their options better and clearly through consolidated dormitory information, since it provided all the necessary details needed by the students in a single application. In addition, the application is designed and incorporated user-friendly features as part of the digitalization process that aided users as they navigated through the application. And lastly, the application strived to promote safety in line with the goals of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (UN SDG) 11.

The core features and functionalities of the application are: detailed listing, geographic information system (GIS) mapping, search, sort, and filtering, scheduling tool, chat facility, expert recommendation module, verified accounts, notification services, transaction history board, digital contract, and ratings and reviews. Altogether, these features and functionalities support the goal of Dormee to provide a platform for the students to navigate, connect, and secure a suitable housing. While the primary target audience for this application is the college students of Bacolod City, it also serves landlords by providing a platform for them to work on their operations. The landlords use the platform to connect with potential tenants and in return secure some at the end of the day. Moreover, there are seven universities within the application which are selected based on three criteria: location on the map relative to the four cardinal directions, prominence, and Commission on Higher Education (CHED) accreditation. The universities that are involved are the following: Carlos Hilado Memorial State University Alijis Campus), Carlos Hilado Memorial State University (Fortune Towne Campus), STI West Negros University, University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos, University of Saint La Salle, Colegio San Agustin – Bacolod, and National University. The universities There are at least ten dormitories per university that are filtered based on the distance criterion: A walking distance of 0.25 miles (400m) or five minutes.^[7]

The limitations of the platform include limited types of cards in the identity verification process, reliance of the dormitory information update on the manual entry of landlords, limited document types in the notarized digital contract verification, chat facility supporting only texts, and ratings and reviews accessible only to users with active dormitory. Moreover, limitations in language support and device compatibility to web are

identified as well. Nonetheless of these constraints, the platform has the potential for a breakthrough in the real estate industry market concerning student housing.

2 METHODOLOGY

The project utilized the Waterfall methodology for the development of the application. This linear approach is well suited to the defined scope and requirements of the project as well to the team structure of three. The sequential phases of planning and analysis, data gathering, system design, and implementation and testing enabled clear task organization and system progress. Each phase was completed and reviewed to ensure the requirements are met. This methodology supported the development of a stable and reliable, user-centered application incorporating seamless user experiences.

2.1 Design and Implementation Constraints

This section focuses on the challenges and limitations that were identified by the team to be affecting the development and implementation of the application. These are composed of user, technological, and data constraints. The user constraints involved digital literacy, language support, and room match and student preferences. Technological constraints included device compatibility and map scalability. As for the data constraints, it contains the following: data availability, data analytics, search criteria, and transaction history. These limitations were thoughtfully considered to ensure that the application is at its superior level.

As for the user constraints, the application has the demographics of both students and landlords. The application requires adequate digital literacy for full and seamless user experience. Meanwhile, the application covers only the English language since it is considered as the universal language. Moreover, the listing search mainly relies on the user preferences. These constraints significantly affect the application in terms of demand and user engagement.

As for the technological constraints, Dormee is a mobile application therefore the devices covered are only phones and tablets. Moreover, it only supports Android. It is advised to follow the minimum requirements for software and hardware for optimal performance. It is in the best interest of the user to use up-to-date and competent devices with current standards.

As for the data constraints, the data availability of the current setup covers only publicly posted and house-to-house interviews of dormitory listings. Data analytics within the application covers limited areas such as financial, user, property, and experience and engagement analytics. In search process, parameters are taken as they are. Only those parameters that match are

recommended and others are restricted from the view of the users. Lastly, the transaction history feature of the application is mainly for record keeping and tracking. The application does not support in-application payment gateways. Therefore, personal transactions must be made and transaction information relies on manual entries made by the landlords.

2.2 Operating Environment

This section outlines the environment in which Dormee operated. Since Dormee is a cross-platform mobile application, its hardware and software requirements are aligned with its nature. These requirements are necessary for the application to function effectively and appropriately. Moreover, the operating environment of Dormee is envisioned to provide a positive and smooth user experience through careful consideration and planning.

The hardware requirements for the application are specified for Android. The user must have a processor of at least a 1.1GHz (Quad-core) to handle multiple tasks and applications concurrently. A minimum memory of 2GB is required for the application to function smoothly alongside other processes and applications. Meanwhile, the device must have a free space of 16GB in its storage to ensure efficient storage and quick access to the application. The minimum hardware requirements for the development of the application for developers are Core i5 or AMD Ryzen 5 processor, 16 GB of RAM, and 256 to 512 GB of SSD storage.

The software requirements cover the environment in which the application was developed and collaborated. In the development, the operating system used was Windows 11 Visual Studio Code is used for coding while Android Studio is used for mobile simulation using emulators. The application was developed using React Native. For server-side logic, Node.js handled backend functionality. Firebase Realtime Database served as the primary data storage solution. The tools to be used in the development are the following: Socket.IO, Google Maps Platform, Geocoding, Distance Matrix, Azure Face, OneSignal, Google Calendar, EmailJS, Cloudinary, Hetzner, OCR Space and Twilio. The team collaborated using Microsoft Teams, Messenger, and Google Drive. Lastly, the design implementation was conducted in Canva and Figma.

The connectivity requirements highlight the network connection as a need to run and utilize the application. The network connection includes mobile data and internet. A reliable network connection in terms of upload speed must be at least five to ten megabits per second (Mbps), while a download speed of twenty to thirty megabits per second (Mbps) is needed. To ensure a seamless user experience and application performance, a stable and fast network connection is

crucial for accessing and utilizing the application. Regarding device compatibility, the application is designed to run on either phones or tablets.

2.3 Features and Functionalities

As showcased in Figure 1, the system comprises of the following main modules: account creation and management, dorm listings, user alerts and reminders, data analytics, admin dashboard, and report module. The main modules contain sub-modules which includes the signup, sign in, user profile management, search, filter, sort, bookmarking, expert recommendation module, scheduling tool, chat facility, ratings and reviews, activity notifications, transaction history board, financial analytics, user analytics, engagement and experience analytics, property analytics, user management, listing management, and request management. The account creation and management module is for authentication allowing access to the application, as well as personalization of personal information. The dorm listings module is mainly for navigation and connection. The discovery of listings, establishment of booking with landlords, inquiry for a listing, and leaving a review are covered in this module. The user alerts and reminders fall under the notification services of the application which aims to provide real-time updates on user activities. The transaction history board that is used for record keeping and tracking is covered in this module as well. Data analytics provide insights regarding financial, user, engagement and experience, and property of a user. The admin dashboard module allows management of user, listing, and request. Lastly, report module is a functionality allowing user to make a report regarding a user, listing, or system performance.

Figure 1: Dormee Decomposition Chart.

Account Creation and Management: Users sign up as Student or Landlord, login, and verify their accounts and identity. Users provide personal information such as name, date of birth, and gender. Meanwhile, the landlord has to provide photos of documents. The user has the option to upload a profile picture. Users are

required to verify their account either through contact number or email. Additionally, the user must undergo identity verification where the user provides a photo of a valid ID and a selfie.

Sign Up: The user is considered as not existing or registered in the application. The user has the option to sign up using an email address or use the Google or Facebook sign up. The user is asked to choose a role, either a Student or Landlord.

Sign In: Existing users are asked to enter their credentials. The email address of the user must match its corresponding password. After a successful authentication, the user is given access to the respective homepage. In case of failed authentication, users are able to change their password using the forgot password function.

User Profile Management: The user is asked to provide necessary details such as first name, last name, gender, and date of birth. Additionally, the user has the option to upload a profile picture. All information is reflected to the user profile and is editable in the future.

Dorm Listings: This covers all the information of a listing as well as function needed for interactions. The listing includes information such as title, price, location, availability, description, payment terms, amenities, rules, as well as photos. There are quick inquiry and schedule buttons provided. A link to the landlord profile provides further information on the landlord.

Search: This functionality allows users to navigate certain listings based on given criteria. The search bar allows users to enter a query such as title keywords. This narrows down the view of the listings that matches the needs and preferences of the user.

Sort: This functionality is an added feature that further narrows down the listing view. The sort function includes newest, highest to lowest, lowest to highest, and most popular. The results are sorted accordingly.

Bookmarking: The users are allowed to save their favorite listings so that they are able to easily locate them again. This function helps user organize their favorite listings in one area. This aids users in comparing listings as they make a decision.

Expert Recommendation Module: This module generates top three recommendations of dormitory listings to students. The users are asked of questions regarding their needs and preferences which are presented in a guided form format. This aids users in their decision making, ensuring that they secure the most suitable one.

Scheduling Tool: Users are able to book a visit using the scheduling tool. This function is under each dormitory listing. This allows users to select their

preferred date and time, and send a request to the landlord. The landlord has the choice to either accept or reject the request, provided that the rejection comes with a reason. The student would be notified of the decision.

Chat Facility: The users are able to communicate within the application. The student has to perform a quick inquiry first in order to create a designated chat interface for both users. Right after, both users are allowed to freely communicate in the chat interface.

Ratings and Reviews: This feature allows students to leave a review to a listing. The student must have an active dormitory to access this feature. The rating is in five-star scale while the review is in commentary format. The review is reflected to the listing and all reviews are aggregated for overall summary.

User Alerts and Reminders: This module is part of the notification service feature of the application. The notification service includes in-application, push, and email services. This feature allows updates of activities of the user for reminder purposes.

Activity Notifications: The activity notifications are either an in-application, push, or email notification. Every activity made by a user constitutes to a notification. This allows user to be updated activities such as new contract from the landlord, reply from landlords, inquiry from a student, near termination contract, and booking status.

Transaction History Board: This feature is mainly for reminders on the end of the student, and monitoring and management on the end of the landlord. The student has the ability to only view their payments. The landlord, however, has the ability to create, edit, and delete payments. The landlord is able to mark a payment as paid for every successful transaction with the student.

Data Analytics: The data analytics covers the following areas: financial, user, property and engagement and experience analytics. This provides insights to landlord regarding their listings and corresponding tenants. This helps landlord make strategies to their business.

Financial Analytics: This involves the total revenue of the property of the landlord. This relies on manual entries based on the payments marked as paid by the landlords. The payments are accumulated to allow landlords to monitor and track their financial progress.

User Analytics: This involves the count of users on a specific listing or overall property. The users are the active tenants of a listing or property. This provides numerical representation of all the tenants that landlord is managing. This helps landlords track and monitor the tenants.

Engagement and Experience Analytics: This involves metrics such as views, inquiries, and reviews. The

views and inquiries metrics are displayed in terms of count. This provides that number of users that have interacted with the listing, giving the landlords insight of the popular preferences of students. Meanwhile, the reviews metric is displayed as individual review and overall summary. This allows landlords to view and gather feedback from the reviews to further enhance the business.

Property Analytics: This involves metrics related to the status and performance of dormitory listings managed by landlords. These metrics include the number of active and inactive listings, room availability, occupancy status, and booking frequency. The data is presented in the form of counts and status indicators, allowing landlords to easily monitor which properties are currently listed, reserved, or fully occupied.

Admin Dashboard: The administrator oversees and maintains the operations within the application. The administrator has an analytics dashboard to provide visual representation of the user distribution, listing status and count, and number of requests in charts and graphs. The administrator has the ability to manage users, listings, and respond to reports.

User Management: In this module, the administrator has the ability to manage users. The administrator has the option to ban or delete users. The administrator must take an action based on a given report.

Listing Management: In this module, the administrator has the ability to manage listings. The administrator is able to view a listing to review its information. The administrator has the option to delete a listing. In the event of policy violation, the administrator has the authority to take an action accordingly.

Request Management: This module allows the administrator to manage requests or reports. The report is viewable including details such as report ID, name of sender, date, purpose of report, message, and attachments. The administrator is able to respond to a report and the respective user would be notified through email.

Report Module: This module allows users to send a report to the administrator. The user must provide details such as purpose, message, and attachments. This module allows maintaining quality of the application.

2.4 Interfaces and Interactions

Dormee featured three user types: students, landlords and administrator. The students navigate listings, connect with landlords, and secure a dormitory. The landlords manage property and listings, connect with students, and manage tenants. Meanwhile, the administrator oversees and manages the operations of the application. Only the interfaces of the core features and functionalities for every user are included for generality.

This is the introduction page of the application where users encounter upon launching the application. It indicates the need and the purpose of the application. As seen in Figure 2, the screen includes the tagline, the objectives and a call-to-action button to get a user started.

Figure 2: Introduction Page.

This is the initial interface wherein users access after the introduction interface in the application. This serves as the entry point for authenticated access. There are three methods to access the application as shown in Figure 3. The methods include using a valid email address or using third-party platforms such as Google or Facebook. This interface allows users to either sign up or login.

Figure 3: Sign Up/Sign In Page.

Figure 4 shows the page that is prompted if the user is registered. If the email address exists, the user is asked to input the respective password. "Send Reset Password Link" is an option where users are able to change their password if forgotten. The user is able to also click on the eye icon to reveal the password for visibility.

Figure 4: Login Password Page.

Figure 5 shows the homepage interface the students are able to access. The interface provides a search bar, compass button, sort and filter options. The main body of the application is where the featured listings are displayed. On the lower right corner is the chatbot button to access the Dormee assistant. On the bottom is the navigation bar which includes the following tabs: homepage, bookmarks, expert, chat and the profile.

Figure 5: Student's Homepage.

The search, sort, and filter interface allows users to refine their search for dormitories based on their specific preferences and needs. The users are able to access the sort and filter functions located at the top of the screen, under the search bar as shown in Figure 6. The search bar is a text field where users enter a query containing keywords. Users filter listings by dormitory and room type, price range, location, and amenities. The sort function enables users to arrange listings by newest, most popular, and by price.

Figure 6: Search, Sort, and Filter.

Figure 7 shows the map interface containing all the listings in the application. There is an option to view the listings in a list view instead. The user is directed to the geographic information system (GIS) Mapping page to see all the available listings in the application. The listings are pinned using their price and availability. The heart icon indicates that the listing has been saved. There is a marker highlighting the school based on the search criteria. Above is a search bar so the students are able to enter a query again. The target icon on the upper right corner allows students to zoom in their current location. The listings are displayed in the bottom as well.

Figure 7: Interactive Map.

As shown in Figure 8, the overview interface includes all key details and landlord information of the listing. In the upper right corner is the bookmark feature. The top most is a carousel for the photos of the listing. Below it is the title, availability, price, location, property type and owner. Furthermore, the listing has two sections: details and reviews. Lastly, it contains buttons for quick inquiry and schedule.

Figure 8: Dormitory Listing.

Figure 9 shows the quick inquiry modal interface which is accessed by the students in a dormitory listing. The purpose of the modal is to allow students to write an inquiry regarding the listing. The modal includes the listing details such as the featured photo, title, price, and location. There is a designated text box where students write freely their message to the landlord.

Figure 9: Quick Inquiry.

The scheduling tool modal interface for students is shown in Figure 10. The modal is accessible in a dormitory listing interface with a designated button for the function. It allows students to plot their preferred date and time of visit. The modal includes a calendar interface which in default shows the current month, day, and year. There is a scroll interface below the calendar with predefined set of time for selection. Dates and time that are in the past becomes inaccessible, indicated by gray formatting. Once the student submits the schedule, a confirmation message prompts.

Figure 10: Student's Scheduling Page.

Figure 11 shows the expert recommendation interface. The expert search provides a form with guided questions regarding the needs and preferences of the students. The form has a total of 7 items including target school, budget, room preferences, dorm type, amenities, proximity, and house rules. One item, namely, the room preferences contain sub-items. The students are required to answer all items to be able to generate a result. Based from the data of the students, the expert recommendation module runs an analysis and determines the top three highest scoring listings to be recommended to the student. The top three results are displayed in the map with corresponding pin markers. The markers display the price and availability of the listings. The target university is highlighted in the middle of the radius circle. The radius circle relies on the proximity answer of the student. It serves as an area visualization for the students to grasp the distance between the dormitories and the university. There are dash lines with distance and travel time for numeric reference. The top three listings are also provided in the bottom. There are displayed using the featured photo, title, location, price, and distance to university.

Figure 11: Expert Recommendation Page.

Figure 12 shows the digital contract interfaces of the students. The first section which is the "Contract Details" contains all key contract details. The top part has the profile photo and name of the landlord, and the status and starting date of the contract. Furthermore, contract details such as start date, completion date, rent amount, water bill, electricity bill, total billed, rental duration, and last billing are provided. The current billing is presented with details of the due date and amount. The second section shows the photo of the verified notarized contract which are printable.

Figure 12: Student's Digital Contract.

The transaction history board interface provides users with a clear, organized view of all their past and current payment transactions as shown in Figure 13. This interface displays detailed records including payment dates, amounts, and statuses. The statuses vary from due now, overdue, late, on-time. The dashboard highlights upcoming payment deadlines and recurring obligations to help users stay on top of their rental obligations. The interface is divided into two sections: not yet paid and already paid. There is an option to view payment instructions for a detailed breakdown of the payment.

Figure 13: Transaction History Board.

Figure 14 shows the homepage interface of the landlords. The left most corner indicates the name of the landlord while the right most corner is the notification bell containing notifications such as inquiries or booking. The homepage shows all the listings created by the landlord. The bottom navigation bar has the homepage, schedule, chat facility, and profile buttons. The floating middle button allows landlords to create a new listing. The listings section interface of the homepage. The listing section contains all the listings created by the landlord. Each listing is displayed with featured photo, title, location, and price. Additionally, experience and engagement analytics are provided for every listing such as the number of views of the listing, number of inquiries made with the listing, and its reviews in average. Every listing is clickable so that the landlords are able to view the details of the listing, as well as manage it by editing or deleting. Moreover, it allows landlords to manage the tenants of the listing, including payments. This section has a button for adding a new listing. Meanwhile, the dashboard section provides data analytics to the landlords regarding their property. The analytics include user, property, financial, and engagement and experience. The analytics are represented in charts and graphs as visualization.

Figure 14: Landlord's Homepage.

The dashboard interface of the landlord displays the key insights derived from user activity as shown in Figure 15. The first analytics is the financial which covers the total revenue of the property based on the accumulated payments of tenants. The user analytics include total active tenants and tenant count per listing and room type. The listing analytics provide information about total active listings and room type breakdown. The experience and engagement analytics involve views, bookings, and messages as metrics for every listing, and the ratings and reviews for experience insights.

Figure 15: Landlord's Dashboard.

Figure 16 shows the interfaces of the scheduling tool of the landlords. This interface displays a calendar view and a list view. In the calendar view, the pending schedule requests and approved requests are indicated in numbers. A mini sub icon is allocated in the cell of the day in the month to show the accumulated scheduled visits. The icon is displayed in a numerical format indicating the total number and is accompanied by a color scheme convention: orange for pending and green for the approved visits. The calendar is filterable by selecting a day. The list view is divided into pending and future visits. A red highlight indicates that the schedule request is conflicting with another request due to overlapping date or time. In this interface, the landlord has the option to approve or reject a request. A rejected request must be provided with a reason.

Figure 16: Landlord's Scheduling Tool.

Figure 17 shows the chat facility interfaces which enable direct and real-time communication between students and landlords after a listing inquiry is initiated. When a student submits an inquiry for a specific dormitory listing, the system automatically redirects the user to the chat interface. The selected listing is attached within the chat for contextual reference. The left image presents the consolidated chat list interface, where all active and previous conversations are displayed in a structured and organized manner. Each chat preview includes the user's profile photo, name, and a snippet of the most recent message, enabling users to quickly identify and prioritize conversations. The right image shows the designated chat thread interface, which displays the full conversation between the student and the landlord in a clean, linear layout. Messages are visually distinguished by alignment and profile photos displayed beside each message, clearly indicating the sender. At the bottom of the interface is a text input field where users are able to compose messages, accompanied by a send button that allows for immediate message delivery.

Figure 17: Chat Facility.

The dashboard interface of administrators provides a consolidated summary of key metrics and system activity as shown in Figure 18. In the top section, the overall statistics such as the total number of active users, property listings, and banned users are displayed. Moreover, visual representations, including charts and graphs, present insights into user distribution, reports overview, and listing status. The bottom section is divided into three sections: users, listings, and reports. The user section contains all the existing users of the application. The listing section contains all listings in the application. Meanwhile, report section contains all the reports received by the administrator.

Figure 18: Administrator's Dashboard.

3 PERFORMANCE TESTING AND EVALUATION

The performance testing and evaluated of Dormee was conducted using the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Product Quality Model, which serves as the strongest framework for assessing the overall quality, effectiveness, and performance of Dormee, assisting the developers in identifying areas of improvement in the application to effectively deliver its intended services to its users. This model provides a more comprehensive structural approach by enabling a systematic assessment of the core features of the application through examining multiple quality attributes, ensuring all components are operating optimally and consistently in all scenarios. The evaluation focuses on the six key quality criteria, namely functional completeness, time behavior, availability, functional appropriateness, functional correctness, confidentiality and recoverability. The criteria fall under various models such as functional suitability, performance efficiency, reliability, and security. These criteria are selected based on the primary objectives of Dormee. Thus, discovery and navigation, personalization, connectivity, and security, and updates between students and landlords across all platforms.

Product Features	Software Quality Models and Attributes	Software Quality Criteria	Mean Score	Feature Mean Score
Detailed Listing	Functional Suitability	Functional Completeness	100.00%	100.00%
GIS Mapping	Performance Efficiency	Time Behavior	90.00%	95.00%
	Reliability	Availability	100.00%	
Search, Sort, and Filtering	Functional Suitability	Functional Correctness	100.00%	100.00%
Expert Recommendation Module	Functional Suitability	Functional Appropriateness	100.00%	100.00%
Scheduling Tool	Functional Suitability	Functional Correctness	100.00%	100.00%
Chat Facility	Reliability	Availability	100.00%	92.59%
	Performance Efficiency	Time Behavior	88.89%	
	Security	Confidentiality	88.89%	
Verified Accounts	Security	Confidentiality	100.00%	100.00%
Transaction History Board	Reliability	Recoverability	100.00%	100.00%
Digital Contract	Functional Suitability	Functional Correctness	90.00%	90.00%
Ratings and Reviews	Functional Suitability	Functional Correctness	90.00%	90.00%
Notification Service	Performance Efficiency	Time Behavior	100.00%	100.00%

Table 1: Summary of Features, Attributes, and Results.

The interpretation scale used in this evaluation provides an understanding of the quality attribute score of each core product feature. As shown in Table 2, the interpretation framework employed the use of the Likert Scale in order to provide descriptive meaning per score range, allowing the developers to better understand the quality of level achieved. This allows for further future enhancements for the betterment of the application.

Score Range (%)	Description	Interpretation
80% – 100%	Very Good	The quality performance of the application feature is at an excellent and desired level.
60% – 79%	Good	The quality performance of the application feature is satisfactory, with minor improvements recommended.
40% – 59%	Average	The quality performance of the application feature is fair, and improvements are required.
20% – 39%	Poor	The quality performance of the application feature is below acceptable standards and requires major improvements.
1% – 19%	Very Poor	The quality performance of the application feature is unacceptable, and system redesign is highly recommended.

Table 2: Validation Testing Results Interpretation.

3.1 User Acceptance

In the acceptance testing, A structured questionnaire was used to assess the performance of Dormee across multiple nonfunctional requirements. The evaluation was distributed through Google Forms, allowing the participants to evaluate the system immediately after being presented with the core features of the application. The questionnaire uses a five-point Likert Scale in every item with five being the highest and one being the lowest. However, the demonstration and testing were conducted face-to-face. These participants evaluated Dormee based on various predefined software quality criteria. A total of 54 respondents completed the survey, specifically there were 21 Information Technology students, 20 non-IT students, eight visitors, one university professor, and three Information Technology (IT) professionals. All the personal information of the respondents are kept confidential.

Mean scores were computed and interpreted for each criterion using the standard ranges shown in Table 3. A higher score means greater agreement or satisfaction. The three highest and lowest criteria are identified and given an analysis to determine which areas meet user satisfaction and those that still lack and need improvement.

Mean Score Range	Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Very Good
3.41 – 4.20	Good
2.61 – 3.40	Average
1.81 – 2.60	Poor
1.00 – 1.80	Very Poor

Table 3: Survey Results Interpretation.

All criteria fall within the ‘Very Good’ range and accordingly received the highest interpretation as shown in Table 4. The highest-rated criteria are accuracy (4.66), generality (4.61), software system independence (4.60), and training (4.60). The top-scoring criteria reflect strong user confidence in the system’s clarity, adaptability, and usability. On contrary, the lowest-rated criteria of Dormee are security (4.40), hardware independence (4.37), and instrumentation (4.37). These need further improvement and continuous enhancement on security prompts, flexibility, and internal monitoring. Overall, the range of mean scores of the survey results is between 4.37 to 4.66.

Criteria	Mean Score	Interpretation
Accuracy	4.66	Very Good
Auditability	4.48	Very Good
Communication Commonality	4.52	Very Good
Completeness	4.57	Very Good
Conciseness	4.42	Very Good
Consistency and Understandability	4.50	Very Good
Controllability	4.49	Very Good
Data Commonality	4.42	Very Good
Decomposability	4.54	Very Good
Error Tolerance	4.53	Very Good
Execution Efficiency	4.46	Very Good
Expandability	4.47	Very Good
Generality	4.61	Very Good
Hardware Independence	4.37	Very Good
Instrumentation	4.37	Very Good
Modularity	4.44	Very Good
Observability	4.51	Very Good
Operability	4.46	Very Good
Security	4.40	Very Good
Self-documentation	4.50	Very Good
Functional Simplicity	4.59	Very Good
Structural Simplicity	4.59	Very Good
Code Simplicity	4.53	Very Good
Software System Independence	4.60	Very Good
Traceability	4.54	Very Good
Training	4.60	Very Good

Table 4: Summary of Survey Results.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion of this research paper addresses the identified problem statements and outlines possible enhancements for future improvement. It summarizes the key findings and highlights the major outcomes

achieved throughout the system development process. This section aims to provide a clear and comprehensive synthesis of the study and its overall contributions.

4.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, Dormee addresses the challenges encountered by students in finding a suitable dormitory by streamlining the housing search process and establishing direct communication between students and landlords. The platform integrates essential features such as dormitory listings, location-based search, messaging, scheduling, and user reviews, digital contract, expert recommendation module, verified accounts, and notifications, which collectively enhance transparency, accessibility, and convenience. Despite challenges experienced during the development process, particularly in data gathering and refining system functionality, the project successfully realized its objective of providing a centralized and reliable dormitory finder platform. Through continuous refinement and user feedback, Dormee demonstrates its value as an effective tool that supports informed housing decisions and promotes a safer and more organized student accommodation environment.

4.2 Recommendations

The proposed enhancements aimed at further improving the functionality, accessibility, and efficiency of the Dormee mobile application. The recommendations are based on the system evaluation results, observed limitations during development and testing, and potential future user needs. These suggested improvements focus on strengthening communication between users, increasing inclusivity through language support, and streamlining transactional processes within the platform. Implementing these recommendations would enhance user experience, operational efficiency, and overall system scalability, ensuring that Dormee remains responsive to the evolving requirements of both students and landlords.

4.2.1 AI-Powered Chatbot Facility

For efficiency in terms of communication between the landlords and the students. Dormee must integrate an AI-powered chatbot to eliminate the process of message approvals on the side of the landlords and to detect spam or inappropriate messages. The chatbot answers the inquiries of user according to the user input. This feature allowed users to have seamless communication and efficient process handling.

4.2.2 Multi-Language Support

In order to further improve the accessibility of the application, Dormee must incorporate multilingual functionality. This functionality allows reaching a wider target audience. Furthermore, users navigate the application and view dormitory information in their

preferred language. The application also promotes inclusivity by eliminating language barriers, which ensures that all students make well-informed housing decisions regardless of their linguistic background.

4.2.3 Integrated Payment System

Dormee must integrate a payment gateway to facilitate monetary transactions. Students pay for reservation fees or early deposits directly through the application. This streamlines the reservation process and further minimizes the need for personal visits or meetings.

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